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Research Article

DOCTORS UNHAPPINESS AND MOTIVES FACTS BEHIND THE ISSUES FACED BY THE DOCTORS IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim and objective of our study and research is to highlight and find out that the insight about the doctors to be unhappy is true and to know about the prompting reasons of unhappiness among doctors.

Methodology: The collection of the information carried out with the utilization of the well organized questionnaire. This research work is a transverse study which carried out for a period of complete 2 years in two tertiary health care centers of Lahore. The information about demography and the perception of evaluating the data of overall doctors being present with unhappiness in our country Pakistan, and collection of their level of personal satisfaction in their life also carried out. Probable reasons for the prevalence of unhappiness among physicians from a many factors explored out. In the final stage, we asked the participants to tell about their intension in the near future to leave or remain in our country Pakistan. We used the SPSS V. 17 for the statistical analysis of the collected information.

Results: In our total assessment and observation 601 (49.0% male doctors) with an average age of twenty eight years were the part of this survey. Most of the participants as 65.0% (n: 393) were the doctors of junior stage. Total 59.0% participants were present with the belief that overall doctors in our country Pakistan are not happy. When we asked them directly about the unhappiness level, participants provided almost equivocal answer (43.0% dissatisfied versus 42.0% satisfied). High load of work (73.0%), less pay (87.0%), no optimistic feedback (70.0%), insecurity of job (64.0%) and adverse mutual support (47.0%) being the very important reasons accountable for the unhappiness. High amount of the doctors (55.0%) were present with preference to live in other countries in comparison with Pakistan.

Conclusion: The results off this research work showed that unhappiness among doctors is worldwide perception, doctors from Pakistan have no exception. High amount of the doctors having intension to leave the country is a very important issue of concern for the services of health care field. It is very necessary to identify the reasons and take remedies to cut those causes.

Key Words: Survey, research work, methodology, Unhappy, doctors, physicians, worldwide, participants.

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INTRODUCTION:

In the countries which are under development as Pakistan with not up to mark system of health care, this issue is performing a vital role in the promotion of brain drain from our country Pakistan. For the treatment of the unhappiness among physicians it is very important to discover the probable reasons of this issue. So, this research work aimed to find out that if the perception about the physicians of being not happy is correct and to examine the prompting reasons for this problem. The unhappiness among doctors is a phenomenon prevailing in the whole world [1]. Different research works from whole world elaborate the decreased morale among physician but there is deficiency of the information about the causes of this issue. Among the possible reasons of unhappiness, most obvious reasons are unsuitable pay and high load of work [2]. But the evidences from the modern world with effective systems, high salary and excellent propose that physicians do not certify the high level of morale. Other possible reasons may be because of alterations in expectations of society, patients and governments about the profession of the medical field. Negative coverage of media, harassment at work places are also some important causes stated in the field as prompting factors in the incidence of unhappiness among the professionals of the medical field [3-5]. It is very important to identify that health-care service operated by demoralized physicians cannot reach up to embellishment. Less satisfaction from job and unhappiness has adverse impacts on the mental and physical well-being of the doctors but it can cause the adverse care of patients as well as clinical administration [6].

METHODOLOGY:

Ethical committee of the Services Hospital gave the permission to conduct this research work. This

transverse research work carried out among doctors in 2 hospitals in the city of Lahore. We invited all the doctors present in the duration of the study period with the utilization of the self-organized questionnaire. We used the descriptive statistics for the presentation of the findings. We got the informed consent from all the doctors on the same well-structured questionnaire, which was according to the standard of the past research works about this matter [1,2]. We piloted first the physicians performing their duties in the department of psychiatry to eliminate the discrepancies and we made some alterations according to their suggestions. We ensured the anonymity in the questionnaire for the encouragement of the participation. We collected the forms on the same day by the team of data collection. There was demographic information in the first section of this organized questionnaire.

We put the question about unhappiness of the doctors in the country. After that this questionnaire investigated the causes of this problem among physicians. We asked the participants in the last to comment on their idea of leaving or remaining in Pakistan in near future. SPSS V.17 was in use for in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information.

RESULTS:

The rate of response was 92.50. We collected no information from the doctors who were not willing to participate. And no information about those doctors was present for analysis. We approached total six hundred and fifty doctors in which six hundred and one showed their willing to participate in the research work. The traits of demography of the patients are present in Table-1.

Table-I: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents. (Total n=601)

Demographic Characteristics		No / Mean	Percent / $\pm$ SD
Age	(Mean $\pm$ SD)	28.8	5.95
Gender	Male	294.0	48.90
	Female	221.0	36.80
Marital status	Single	321.0	53.40
	Married	210.0	34.90
	Separated	17.0	2.80
Grade	House officer	186.0	30.90
	Postgraduate trainee	207.0	34.40
	Resident Medical Officer	81.0	13.50

	Registrar	22.0	3.70
	Consultant	29.0	4.80
	Demonstrators(Basic Sciences)	35.0	5.80
Specialty	Medicine and Allied	362.0	60.20
	Surgeryand Allied	239.0	39.76

No high salary (87.0%), high level of workload (73.0%) and insecurity of the job (64.0%) were the most important reasons of discontentment among the physicians performing their duties in Pakistan. A large proportion of the participants (55.0%) were present with the preferences to be in other countries because

of these causes (Table-2A and 2B). Overall 59.20% (n: 356) doctors were agree with the opinion about being no happy in their country (Table-2). Regardless of showing their agreement with this opinion, 42.0% participants showed some satisfaction level, when we asked them about the unhappiness level.

Table-II A: Unhappiness among doctors in Pakistan - Respondents Views

Factors Studied	Number	Percent
Do you think that overall Physicians in Pakistan are unhappy?	Number	Percent
Yes	356.0	59.20
No	125.0	20.80
Don't know	61.0	10.10
When you think about your life at the moment, would you say that by and large, you are satisfied with your life and are you mostly dissatisfied?		
Extremely dissatisfied	51.0	8.50
Dissatisfied	201.0	33.80
Not sure	80.0	13.30
Satisfied	220.0	36.60
Extremely satisfied	31.0	5.20

Table-II B: Factors studied for unhappiness among doctors in Pakistan.

Causes of doctor's unhappiness in our country	Affirmative	
	No	Percent
Less pay	524	87.2
Increased workload	439	73
No positive feedback for good work	426	70.9
Increase workplace stress	388	64.6
Decrease in team work spirit	264	43.9
Decrease in control over work environment	213	35.4
Harassment	212	35.3
Demanding patients	212	35.3
Making trade-off decisions due to resource constrained environment	205	34.1
No job security.	383	63.7
Difficulties in balancing work/ home life	321	53.4
Poor mutual support	284	47.3
Decreased respect	283	47.1
Loss of patients trust	182	30.3
Increased use of protocols, guidelines	172	28.6

Difficult job	162	27
Any other factor	146	24.3
A growing culture of blame	273	45.4
Emotionally demanding work	191	31.8
Media being hostile	188	31.3
Aggression and violence faced at work	188	31.3
Increased accountability	119	19.8

DISCUSSION:

Our complete research work was relying on the self-reporting questionnaire just like many research works of the past which can be the result of bias. Most of the participants of this research work (59.0%) support the perception that they were not happy in the country. This result was in favor of many research works conducted in the past in the whole world [1,7,8]. A constant amount (28.0%) doctors and other professionals of the health care field are available to have the high levels of threshold of stress in comparison to the 18.0% in the normal population [9,10]. Some research works have found that majority of the physicians are happy and they found no reduction in the morale and professional excellence [11,12]. Most of the doctors were not happy similar to many other research works due to the current scenario prevailing in the country and in the health care field but many physicians showed their satisfaction on the level of individual [11].

Low salary (87.0%), high level of workload (73.0%) and insecurity of the job (64.0%) are the most important reasons for the unhappiness among doctors which is much close to past works [1,13]. One of the

supposition of the findings of the research work may be that the doctor's training in the medical institutes are not preparing the physicians of in accordance with the real environment of the hospital. Most of the doctors are working in an environment which is present with limited resources. The training of the doctors in the strict and complicated institutes can lead them to the stress. Low level of encouragement to team work in the medical field can also lead the situation to stress [14]. High level of stress can lead to the high prevailing danger of medical errors as well as high expense in the delivery of health care with the increase of the adverse quality care and absenteeism of the professionals of health care field [15]. High amount of the doctors showed their intention to leave Pakistan in future provided the same trends of the society. Stress at the places of work, financially instability and issues of security are some of the factors accountable for this trend [16,17].

The utilization of the convenience sampling technique is not much ideal. There are some limitations of this research work. The findings of the research work were not valid for the doctors working in general hospitals in the same city of Lahore. Now, there is need of the

systematic approach to tackle the issue. There is need to accept these reasons and adopt valuable steps to tackle these problems on the level of organization, better incentives, proper structure of the job and suitable hours of working will also help the profession in the solutions of the medical errors.

CONCLUSION:

The proper training of leadership and encouragement of the team work can reduce the stress among doctors. The workshops for the management of the level of stress among individual, counseling of carrier, free counseling and services of psychotherapy are some steps which can support the development of morale and satisfaction about job. The findings of this research work showed that unhappiness among doctors is very serious issue in the field of tertiary health care facility.

REFERENCES:

1. Laurence M. Why are doctors so unhappy? Reducing working hours might help. *BMJ* 2001;322:1361-2.
2. Mechanic D. Physician discontent. *JAMA* 2003;290:941-6.
3. Zuger A. Dissatisfaction with medical practice. *N Engl J Med* 2004;350:69-75.
4. Smith R. Why are doctors so unhappy? *BMJ* 2001;322:1073-4.
5. Edwards N, Kornacki MJ, Silversin J. Unhappy doctors: What are the causes and what can be done. *BMJ* 2002;324:835-8.
6. Senewiratne IB. Emigration of doctors: A problem for the developing and the developed countries. (Part1) *Br Med J* 1975;1(5958):618-20.
7. Khan MM. The NHS International Fellowship Scheme in Psychiatry: Robbing the poor to pay the rich? *Psychiatric Bulletin* 2004;28:435-7.
8. Firth-Cozens J. New stressors, new remedies. *Occup Med (Lond)* 2000;50:199-201.
9. Jones JW, Barge, BN, Steffy BD, Fay LM, Kunz LK. Stress and medical malpractice: Organizational risk assessment and intervention. *J Applied Psychol* 1988;4:727-35.
10. Imran N, Jawaid M, Haider II, Masood Z. Bullying of junior doctors in Pakistan: A cross sectional survey. *Singapore Med J* 2010;51(7):592-5.
11. Nylenna M, Gulbrandsen P, Forde R, Aasland OG. Job satisfaction among Norwegian general practitioners. *Scand J Prim Health Care* 2005;23:198-202.
12. Nylenna M, Gulbrandsen P, Forde R, Aasland OG. Unhappy doctors? A longitudinal study of

life and Job satisfaction among Norwegian doctors 1994-2002. *BMC Health Serv Res* 2005, Jun 8;5:44 doi 10.1186/1472-6963.

13. Wall TD, Bolden RI, Borrill CS, Carter AJ, Golya DA, Hardy GE, et al. Minor psychiatric disorders in NHS trust staff: occupational and gender differences. *Br J Psychiatry* 1997;171:519-23.
14. Firth-Cozens J. The psychological problems of doctors. In: Firth-Cozens J, Payne R. *Stress in health professionals: Psychological and organizational causes and interventions*. London: Wiley, 1999.
15. Magee M, Hojat M. Impact of health care system on physicians' discontent. *J Community Health* 2001;26:357-65.
16. Murray A, Montgomery JE, Chang H, Rogers WH, Inui T, Safran DG. Doctor discontent. A comparison of physician satisfaction in different delivery system settings, 1986 and 1997. *J Gen Intern Med* 2001;16:452-9.
17. Manthorpe J, Stanley N, Caan W. Is depression a workplace issue? *Professional Soc Work* 2002; Feb:12-13.